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A Cross-Sectional Study to Assess the Adult Lebanese Population's Knowledge, Attitudes, and Practices Regarding Annual Influenza Vaccination

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KEYWORDS

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ABSTRACT

Introduction and Goals: Annual influenza vaccination has been shown to be one of the most effective ways of preventing influenza and its complications. In Lebanon, national data on influenza vaccination rates are still unavailable. Furthermore, there are no well-defined national educational programs to raise awareness. The study's main goals were to evaluate influenza vaccination rates among the Lebanese adult population, to understand the factors that influence people's attitudes toward influenza vaccination, and to develop effective strategies to increase influenza vaccination awareness, knowledge, and acceptance.

Method: A quantitative cross-sectional design was used to figure out how many people got a flu shot during the 2018-2019 flu season. A total of 570 people aged 18 and up were randomly selected from various locations in Beirut via phone calls, including large shopping malls, recreational areas, and universities. A questionnaire with 27 questions was used to assess knowledge, attitude, and habits.

Results: The overall influenza vaccine uptake rate in 2018–2019 was 21%. Males (27%), the elderly (100%), widowed (72%), employed (37%), those in good financial circumstances (42%), healthcare workers (63%), and those with a low level of education (57%) all had significantly higher immunization rates. Furthermore, those who sought medical advice on a regular basis (47%), as well as those with one or more chronic disorders (29%), had high vaccination rates. Moreover, higher vaccination rates were associated with increased awareness of influenza and its vaccine ($p < .001$).

Conclusion: In Lebanon, influenza vaccine uptake remains unsatisfactory. This is primarily due to a misunderstanding of the severity of influenza and the effectiveness of influenza vaccination. As a result, national awareness and immunization efforts are urgently needed. Additional cause-and-effect research studies in Lebanon would yield more reliable indicators of the influenza vaccine's effectiveness. Such research would boost confidence in the vaccine's protective and positive effects.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Influenza viruses are what cause seasonal influenza, a respiratory infection. It occurs primarily in the winter in temperate climates and all year in tropical and subtropical climates. The influenza A and B viruses are the most common cause of human influenza infections, afflicting people of all ages and causing symptoms such as fever, dry cough, sore throat, runny nose, headache, and muscle aches. The severity of illness varies from person to person, ranging from mild respiratory symptoms to severe infections such as pneumonia, which may necessitate hospitalization and can result in death, especially in high-risk patients such as people 65 and older [1] and young infants under the age of 5 years [2]. Seasonal influenza can affect anyone, but some people are more vulnerable than others. These people include healthcare workers (HCW) who are at high risk of being exposed to suspected or confirmed influenza patients for an extended period of time, as well as people who are at a higher risk of serious complications, such as young infants under the age of five, the elderly, pregnant women, asthmatics, diabetics, immunocompromised patients, and patients with heart or lung diseases [3].

The flu vaccine is one of the most important ways to stop the flu and its effects during flu season. The World Health Organization (WHO) and the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) both recommend an annual flu vaccine as the most effective way to prevent infection, particularly in people who are predisposed to influenza complications [3, 4].

The influenza season in Lebanon typically lasts from September to April, with a noticeable peak during the winter months. During this time, many people are affected by suspected or confirmed influenza, leading to absenteeism from school and work. Furthermore, people suffering from serious illnesses or high-risk patients may require hospitalization due to increased morbidity and its consequences. Moreover, a significant number of Lebanese people live abroad and visit the country frequently during the summer, with a noticeable increase during the summer. Furthermore, "this population mix, with different demographic characteristics, makes the country prone to co-circulation, thereby increasing the danger of mutation of different influenza viruses," according to the WHO. It is possible for the virus to spread from person to person via droplets or indirect contact routes, particularly in congested areas such as schools, nurseries, and healthcare facilities. This risk is greater in poorer areas of Lebanon, where infection control and prevention measures, such as safe food and water, and access to personal hygiene services, are lacking.

Furthermore, there is no national data on influenza vaccination rates. Additionally, national vaccination programs and educational campaigns to raise influenza awareness and prevention are ill-defined or non-existent. "What are the measures that persuade Lebanese people to receive the annual influenza vaccination in light of this?" As a result, the spread of influenza infections is reduced, as are costs and hospitalizations, as well as morbidity and mortality among the vulnerable population.

The main point of our research was to find out how many adults in Lebanon got a flu shot during the 2018-2019 season. Furthermore, the goals of our study were to:

- Identify factors that influence Lebanese people's and HCW's decision to get a seasonal influenza vaccine, and
- Come up with effective ways to get more people vaccinated against the flu in Lebanon through vaccine education and awareness programs.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Study design and sample size

During the 2018–2019 flu season, a quantitative cross-sectional design was used to find out what percentage of the Lebanese population got a flu shot. The research was carried out in Beirut, Lebanon's capital. A total of 570 adults aged 18 and up were chosen at random from various areas of Beirut. Through phone calls, interviewees were chosen at random from various regions of Beirut. Furthermore, interviews were conducted in large shopping malls, recreational areas, and universities throughout Beirut. The study's objectives were explained to the participants, and their verbal consent was obtained for their participation in the study.

2.2 Investigation tool

Based on published studies and a review of the research on similar surveys [3, 4, 5], a questionnaire with 27 questions was made. This questionnaire was used to find out how often people got flu shots for the 2018-2019 season, as well as what they knew, how they felt, and what they did about flu and vaccinations. Before being adjusted, the questionnaire was piloted and tested on 40 people.

2.3 Data analysis

For data entry and analysis, SPSS 16.0 software was used. To evaluate the 27 indicators, descriptive statistics were used. Variables were described with percentages and frequencies. The association between categorical variables was measured using a chi-squared statistical test. P values less than or equal to 0.05 were considered statistically significant for vaccine uptake.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Sociodemographic factors and medical history

Our participants were mostly female (69%) and married (62%). 61% were between the ages of 30 and 64, 37% were under the age of 30, and only 2% were 65 or older. More than half of our population (52%) had a high school diploma, 29% had a university diploma, 8% had less than a high school diploma, 6% had graduate studies, and 5% did not attend school at all. Only 40% of our population was employed, 82% reported a manageable financial situation, and 84% had public medical insurance. Only 71 (12%) of the 570 participants work in the medical field. 161 (28%) of the 570 participants seek medical advice on a regular basis, while 409 (72%) seek medical assessment only when necessary. In terms of chronic diseases, 9% of our participants had heart disease, 3% had respiratory disease, 2% were diabetic, 1% had cancer, and 1% had kidney disease; additionally, 7% had more than one chronic disease.

3.2 Influenza infections and vaccine uptake rates

Between September 2018 and April 2019, 428 of our participants, or 75%, said they had flu or an illness like flu, such as a fever, cough, sore throat, or pain in their muscles and joints. In terms of the annual flu shot, 448 of our participants did not receive one between September 2018 and March 2019. On the other hand, 122 of our participants got a flu shot. This gave us an overall uptake rate of 21% for the flu shot.

3.3 Factors influencing participants' attitudes toward influenza vaccine use

Of the 122 people who were vaccinated, 36% said they did it to protect themselves and others from infection as well as to follow their doctor's recommendations; they also said they had previous good experience with influenza vaccination. Table 1 shows the remaining factors.

Table 1. Reasons for Getting an Influenza Vaccination

Variables	N = 122 (%)
To protect myself and others, a physician's recommendation and good experience with vaccines are needed.	44 (36%)
44 (36%)	20 (16%)
To protect myself and others, physician recommendation, having a chronic medical condition	12 (10%)
20 (16%)	12 (10%)
To protect myself and others from infection.	11 (9%)
12 (10%)	7 (6%)
To protect myself and others from infection, I followed my employer's recommendation.	7 (6%)
12 (10%)	5 (4%)
To protect myself and others, physician recommendations, national recommendations.	2 (2%)
11 (9%)	2 (2%)

On the other hand, 37% of the 448 people who were not vaccinated against influenza said it is a mild illness, 16% said the vaccine is unnecessary and there are no national recommendations to take it, 15% said the vaccine is expensive and unnecessary, and 8% said they are afraid of needles. Table 2 depicts the various reasons why our population is declining in influenza vaccination.

Table 2. Reasons for Low Vaccination Rates Against Influenza

Variables	N = 448 (%)
Influenza is a mild illness.	166 (37%)
166 (37%)	75 (17%)
The vaccine isn't necessary, and there aren't any national recommendations to get it.	68 (15%)
75 (17%)	36 (8%)
The vaccine is expensive, and it is not important.	25 (5%)
68 (15%)	23 (5%)
Fear of needles.	13 (3%)
36 (8%)	13 (3%)
Influenza is a mild illness, and the vaccine is expensive.	9 (2%)
25 (5%)	4 (1%)
The vaccine is not important.	4 (1%)
23 (5%)	4 (1%)
There are no national recommendations for taking it.	4 (1%)
13 (3%)	4 (1%)

Also, the things that made our population (570 people) want to get a flu shot in the future were looked at (table 3). 33% believe that physician recommendations are an important factor in influenza vaccination uptake; 22% believe that national recommendations and awareness programs on television and radio are important; 8% believe that the government should provide the vaccine free of charge; and 6% believe that all the previous reasons could encourage them to get the vaccine in the future. However, 11% of our population stated that nothing could persuade them to get the flu vaccine in the future.

Table 3. Motivating Factors for Getting Vaccinated in the Future

Variables	N = 570 (%)
Physician recommendations	183 (33%)
183 (33%)	125 (22%)
National recommendations and awareness programs on TV and radio	60 (11%)
125 (22%)	44 (8%)
Nothing can encourage me to take it in the future.	36 (6%)
60 (11%)	36 (6%)
National recommendations and awareness programs on TV and radio, if free	28 (5%)
44 (8%)	18 (3%)
Physicians' and national recommendations; awareness programs on TV/radio, if free	18 (3%)
36 (6%)	14 (2%)
Physicians and national recommendations	8 (1%)

3.4 Knowledge about Influenza Infections

The vast majority of people in our country (96%) could describe the signs of having the flu. Half of the people polled thought that influenza can cause serious illness in some way, while 24% said that influenza is "not at all" linked to serious illnesses. Furthermore, 59% of our population thought that pneumonia and death were among the complications caused by influenza infections, while 35% said there were no complications. In terms of high-risk people for influenza, 39% of our population recognized that HCW, infants under the age of five, the elderly, and immunocompromised patients were at high risk. Only 23% thought only immunocompromised patients were at risk, while 19% thought infants under five and the elderly were at greater risk. Concerning ways to avoid getting influenza, the vast majority of people (72%) knew that good hand hygiene and how to cough properly can help, and 23% added getting vaccinated against influenza to the list.

3.5 Knowledge about the influenza vaccine

Almost half of our population (54%) was aware that the influenza vaccine is available in Lebanon, and 47.5% thought it was effective and safe. However, only 26% were aware that the vaccine is required annually. In terms of the likelihood of contracting influenza if vaccination is not obtained, nearly half of our population (52%) thought it was "very low," 24% thought it was "low," and 15% thought it was "high." When it comes to cost, nearly half of people (46%) do not know how much the influenza vaccine costs, 37% believe it is expensive, and 17% believe it is "not expensive." In terms of where people learned about the influenza vaccine, 38% learned about it from schools, neighbors, and Internet searches; 26% learned about it from social media; 11% from family members, friends, or colleagues; 10% from physicians; and 6% from pharmacists.

3.6 Association between sociodemographic factors and vaccination

Table 4 depicts the relationship between sociodemographic factors and influenza vaccination uptake. Except for the health insurance factor, there was a statistically significant association between all tested sociodemographic factors and influenza vaccination uptake among the Lebanese population. Males ($p = 0.035$), the elderly ($p < .001$), widowed ($p < .001$), employed people ($p < .001$), people with a comfortable financial status, and people without schooling had significantly higher levels of vaccination, followed by those with graduate studies ($p < .001$). Furthermore, HCW had a clear and statistically significant higher level of vaccination ($p.001$) than nonmedical workers, with an uptake rate of 63% versus 15%.

Table 4. Association Between Sociodemographic Factors and Influenza Vaccine Uptake

Factors	Influenza vaccine was Administered N = 122 (21%)	Influenza vaccine was not administered N = 448 (79%)	p-value
Gender			
Male	47 (27%)	128 (73%)	0.035
Female	75 (19%)	320 (81%)	
Age			
< 30 years	42 (20%)	169 (80%)	< .001
30–64 years	71 (20%)	279 (80%)	
≥ 65 years	9 (100%)	0 (0%)	
Marital Status			
Single	32 (18%)	146 (82%)	< .001
Married	71 (20%)	281 (80%)	
Divorced	6 (27%)	16 (73%)	
Widowed	13 (72%)	5 (28%)	
Educational Level			
No education	17 (57%)	13 (43%)	< .001
Below high school	5 (11%)	42 (89%)	
High school	34 (11%)	263 (89%)	
University degree	50 (31%)	112 (69%)	
Graduate studies	16 (47%)	18 (53%)	
Employment			
Yes	83 (37%)	143(63%)	< .001
No	39 (11%)	305(89%)	
Financial Status			
Comfortable	30(42%)	42 (58%)	< .001
Manageable	91(19%)	377 (81%)	
Difficult	1(3%)	29 (97%)	
Health Insurance			
None	5 (12%)	38 (88%)	0.110
Public insurance	103 (21%)	377 (79%)	
Private insurance	14 (30%)	33 (70%)	
Medical Field			
Yes	45 (63%)	26 (37%)	< .001
No	77 (15%)	422 (85%)	

3.7 Association between medical history and influenza vaccination

There is a highly significant correlation between people who seek medical advice on a regular basis and influenza vaccination (vaccination rate of 47%) and people who seek medical advice only when absolutely necessary (vaccination rate of 11%; $p.001$). Similarly, with a vaccination rate of 29%, a significant association ($p = 0.03$) was found between people with chronic diseases and influenza vaccination (table 5).

Table 5. Association between Medical History and Influenza Vaccination

Medical History	Influenza vaccine was Administered 122 (21%)	Influenza vaccine was not Administered 448 (79%)	p-value
Medical Advice			
Routinely	75 (47%)	86 (53%)	< .001
When needed	47 (11%)	362 (89%)	
The Presence of Chronic Diseases			
Yes	37 (29%)	91 (71%)	0.03
No	85 (19%)	357 (81%)	

3.8 Association between perceived knowledge about influenza and vaccination

Table 6 depicts the relationship between our population's knowledge of influenza infections and vaccination. A significant high level of vaccination ($p < .001$) was observed among people who believe influenza can cause serious illness "a lot" and those who are aware that influenza can be complicated by pneumonia and death. Concerning influenza prevention measures, a high level of vaccination (78%) was observed among people who believed that hand hygiene and influenza vaccination were effective preventive measures.

Table 6. Association between Perceived Knowledge About Influenza Infections and Vaccination

Knowledge about Influenza infections	Influenza vaccine was administered 122 (21%)	Influenza vaccine was not administered 448(79%)	p-value
Symptoms of Influenza			
Fever, cough, runny nose, sore throat	120 (22%)	431(78%)	0.382
Runny nose	2 (25%)	6 (75%)	
Nausea, vomiting, abdominal pain	0	2 (100%)	
Don't know	0	9 (100%)	
Thinking that Influenza can cause serious illness			
Not at all	11 (8%)	127 (92%)	< .001
A little	36 (55%)	30 (45%)	
Somehow	27 (9%)	263 (91%)	
A lot	47 (67%)	23 (33%)	
Don't know	1 (17%)	5 (83%)	
Complications of Influenza			
Pneumonia, death	93 (28%)	244 (72%)	< .001
No complications	26 (13%)	176 (87%)	
Don't know	3 (10%)	28 (90%)	

3.9 Association between perceived knowledge about influenza vaccine and influenza vaccination

Table 7 depicts the relationship between influenza vaccine knowledge and vaccination. People who believe the vaccine is effective, safe, available in Lebanon, and needed every year have a significantly higher level of vaccination ($p < .001$). Furthermore, people who believed that the risk of getting influenza was "high" or "very high" if the vaccine was not taken had higher vaccination rates ($p < .001$). In addition, there was no difference in vaccination rate (37%) between those who thought the vaccine was "expensive" and those who thought it was "inexpensive."

Table 7. Association Between Knowledge About Vaccines and Vaccination

Knowledge about the Influenza vaccine	Influenza Vaccine was administered 122 (21%)	Influenza vaccine Not was not administered 448(79%)	p-value
Availability of the vaccine in Lebanon			
Yes	107 (35%)	200 (65%)	< .001
No	15 (6%)	248 (94%)	
Effectiveness of the vaccine			
Yes	120 (44%)	150 (56%)	< .001
No	2 (1%)	298 (99%)	
Safety of the vaccine			
Yes	120 (43%)	156 (57%)	< .001
No	2 (1%)	292 (99%)	
Every year, a vaccine is required			
Yes	115 (76%)	36 (24%)	< .001
No	7 (2%)	412 (98%)	
Likelihood of getting Influenza if there is no vaccination			
Very low	4 (1%)	291 (99%)	< .001
Low	18 (13%)	120 (87%)	
High	63 (72%)	25 (28%)	
Very high	31 (94%)	2 (6%)	
Don't know	6 (38%)	10 (62%)	
Thinking that vaccines are expensive			
Yes	78 (37%)	131 (63%)	< .001
No	36 (37%)	61 (63%)	
I don't know the cost	8 (3%)	256 (97%)	

3.10 Association between sources of information about influenza vaccine and influenza vaccination

People who learned about the vaccine from "media, family, friends, and colleagues" (90%), followed by those who learned about it from pharmacists (89%), and physicians (78%), had a highly significant level of vaccination rates ($p < .001$).

3.11 Association between influenza-like illness and vaccination

The relationship between influenza-like illness and vaccination is depicted in Figure 1. According to this figure, 20% of those who reported influenza-like illness were vaccinated, while 25% of those who reported no influenza-like illness were vaccinated. This link is not considered statistically significant ($p = 0.3$).

Figure 1: Association Between Influenza-Like Illness and Vaccination

3.12 Influenza vaccination rates through social media

We conducted a survey poll on Twitter in November 2018 and August 2019 to assess influenza vaccination rates for the 2018–2019 influenza season among Lebanese people. At the start of the 2018–2019 season (N = 208), there was a low vaccination rate of 7%, which increased to 12% by the end of the season (N = 149).

4. DISCUSSION

National data on influenza vaccination rates are not available in Lebanon. Similarly, few studies have been conducted worldwide to assess the overall vaccination rates, knowledge, and practices of the general population regarding seasonal influenza vaccinations. However, several international studies have been conducted to assess these factors among healthcare professionals.

4.1 Vaccination rates for influenza

Between September 2018 and March 2019, our study found that only 21% of the Lebanese population received influenza vaccinations. Lower influenza vaccination rates were also observed among Lebanese Twitter users, with 7% at the start of the 2018-2019 season and 12% at the end. There is no Lebanese national data to compare our findings to; however, these rates are lower than the overall influenza vaccination rates assessed in El Khoury and Salameh's study conducted in Lebanese pharmacies during the 2014–2015 season, which was 27.6% [5]. Low vaccination rates were also observed in the United States, with influenza vaccination coverage among adults ranging between 40 and 45% in CDC studies conducted over the last 6 years [6].

4.2 Social determinants

Our study found that Lebanese men had higher influenza vaccination rates than men in other published studies [7–9]. Similar to what the CDC found, our data showed that the highest vaccination rates were among people 65 and older. In contrast to the findings of El Khoury and Salameh's [5] Lebanese study, the highest vaccination rates were also found among the least educated. This difference could be because samples were only taken from Beirut and not from other cities or rural areas. Most of the people with the least education got the vaccine because their doctor or pharmacist told them to. Also, our study found that the highest rates of vaccination were among people who were working and had stable finances.

In terms of the patient's medical history, our study found a strong link between the number of medical visits and the presence of chronic diseases in relation to the flu shot. This is not surprising, since patients can get advice or the flu shot during medical visits [10]. But 29% of high-risk patients with one or more chronic diseases were not vaccinated as often as they should have been. This demonstrates that this group requires more education and vaccinations.

As expected, the rate of flu vaccination was higher among health care workers (HCW) than among people in other nonmedical jobs. This is mostly because health care workers now know more about influenza and how to stop it. Employer-mandated vaccination requirements also play a role.

Vaccination rates were also higher among widows and divorcees. This could be due to a greater awareness of the importance of maintaining good health among this population, as the majority of them (75%) received the vaccine based on their doctors' recommendations. Several international studies, however, found that being married with social support was associated with higher vaccination rates [11–13] when compared to people living alone with limited assistance, who may have less access to health care facilities and less support from family members. In contrast, one study found that single people had higher vaccination rates than married, widowed, or divorced people [14].

4.3 Influential factors influencing influenza vaccine uptake

Most of the people who have been vaccinated (93%) believe that the flu shot will protect them. In the same way, most people who got vaccinated (75%) did so because their doctors told them to. Also, 36% of people who were vaccinated said they had consistently good experiences with the vaccine, which explains why they keep getting the flu shot. On the other hand, our unvaccinated population (N = 448) didn't want to get flu shots because of two big problems. This population's misconceptions included thinking of influenza as a "mild illness" and believing that the influenza vaccine is "not important" or "expensive."

The assessed factors that made people more likely to get flu shots in the future are suggested as an important tool for the Lebanese MOPH to use. Such a tool could help put into place effective plans to increase the number of Lebanese people, especially high-risk patients, who get flu shots. The role of Lebanese doctors and pharmacists in promoting and encouraging vaccinations, especially among high-risk patients, must be emphasized in these plans. Influenza vaccination recommendations that are disseminated nationally and included in the national vaccination program are critical in increasing trust and uptake rates. The Lebanese government may be able to overcome the cost issue with the assistance of the WHO by providing the vaccine for free or at a low cost.

Because people don't seem to know that vaccines are available, work well, and are safe, an effective education and awareness campaign is needed. Vaccination rates could go up if there were more educational campaigns and programs on TV and radio to raise awareness. In the same way, the people who were studied didn't know that they needed a vaccination every year. In contrast, our study showed that people who think the vaccine works, is safe, is available in Lebanon, and is required every year, are much more likely to get it. People who were aware that influenza could cause serious illness, including pneumonia and death, were much more likely to get vaccinated.

4.4 Influenza-like illness and vaccination

Our study found no statistically significant link between influenza-like illness and influenza vaccination. The most likely explanation is that people incorrectly label any respiratory illness as influenza without performing confirmatory laboratory tests. Human Coronavirus, Parainfluenza,

Rhinoviruses, and Respiratory Syncytial Viruses can all present with clinical symptoms similar to influenza. Multiple studies, however, have found a reduction in influenza infections associated with influenza vaccination in adults [15, 16], children [17], and pregnant women and their infants [18, 19]. One study found a link between influenza vaccination and a reduction in the severity of community-acquired pneumonia during influenza seasons [20]. Another study found that the influenza vaccine reduced severity in hospitalized adult patients with community-acquired influenza [21]. Following the emergence of the novel coronavirus COVID-19, an increase in influenza vaccination rates is thought to be extremely beneficial during influenza seasons, especially among high-risk groups. Improving herd immunity would reduce influenza hospitalizations and increase hospital bed availability for patients with COVID-19 and other respiratory diseases.

5. RECOMMENDATIONS

The Lebanese Ministry of Health (MOPH) can come up with a variety of plans and actions to increase the number of high-risk patients and residents of Lebanon who get flu shots. Such strategies must be accompanied by action plans and follow-ups in order to be implemented on an annual basis. These strategies can be divided into three categories:

- **Education** is a critical component of national influenza vaccination programs. To educate the public about the importance of the flu vaccine, educational awareness campaigns must be well-defined and structured. These campaigns aim to raise public awareness about influenza infections, symptoms, risks, complications, and preventive measures. Campaigns must address all aspects of the importance of getting the flu vaccine every year, such as removing all misconceptions and barriers that keep people from getting vaccinated. Details like where to get the vaccine, as well as its safety and effectiveness, must be addressed. The MOPH may broadcast these campaigns using existing media. Ads on television and radio, newspapers, billboards, pop-up messages on the internet, and the most visited websites in Lebanon can all be used. Email messages and mobile phone text messages, as well as social networks like Facebook and Twitter, are all effective communication methods. Healthcare facilities, dispensaries, schools, and universities are critical components that must be recruited as partners to support national campaigns. Furthermore, pharmacies can be involved because they can play an important role in improving vaccination rates by increasing vaccine awareness and administration throughout the influenza season.
- **Access to vaccines:** The Lebanese government, along with the WHO, plays a key role in making sure that people can get vaccines when they need them. By allocating and reserving the necessary funds, the MOPH should be able to provide the necessary amounts of vaccines at the lowest possible cost. Having enough vaccines available for free or at a low cost will eventually lead to more people getting the flu shot. Also, putting the flu vaccine on the list of vaccines that everyone must get as part of national vaccination programs is a big step toward getting more people to use it. On the other hand, there should be enough vaccines in rural and remote areas. Finally, and most importantly, campaigns should run throughout the flu season rather than just at the beginning.
- **Surveillance:** Beginning in 2014, the MOPH began monitoring for severe acute respiratory infections in several countries as part of the WHO project (SARI). The main goals of this surveillance system were to find the flu virus and track its spread. The main goal of this kind of monitoring is to find out if the viruses' antigenic properties have changed. Every year, these changes are incorporated into the development of global vaccination. As a result, the WHO issues alerts whenever a potential public health threat of global significance manifests. Additional surveillance at the national level is recommended to track and report influenza

vaccination uptake rates. These statistics are critical for prioritizing efforts to increase the population's vaccination rate each year and to reduce the burden and severity of influenza infections, particularly in high-risk groups. The government may make phone calls to gauge uptake rates among a representative sample of the general population.

6. LIMITATIONS

Despite the fact that the survey was conducted only in Beirut and excluded rural areas, the majority of its recommendations are applicable to the public. This constraint may have resulted in selection bias, which may or may not have affected the conclusions and outcomes. To determine representative overall influenza vaccination rates at the national level, a more thorough phone survey that includes residents of remote and rural areas as well as other important Lebanese cities is required. Furthermore, additional correlations may have been statistically validated by a multivariable analysis to assess the relationship between various parameters and outcomes. Another factor that could have influenced the link between vaccination rates and flu infections is a lack of data on hospitalizations caused by flu-like symptoms. Future polls may find it useful to resolve these constraints.

7. CONCLUSION

The uptake of influenza vaccine in Lebanon remains below average. This is primarily due to a misunderstanding of the severity of influenza and the preventive value of the influenza vaccine. As a result, national awareness and immunization efforts are urgently needed. More cause-and-effect research studies (pre- and post-intervention) in Lebanon would provide more robust measures of influenza vaccine effectiveness. Such studies will increase trust in the vaccine's protective and beneficial effects.

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